

The personality

What a species. A long, long history of trying to understand our identity by navel gazing and an equally long history of failing to recognise the overwhelming power of social mechanisms: each unique identity is acquired and 'constructed' and the instrument of identity construction is language. Bang this drum as I will, I have to recognise that what social construction demands is very, very difficult to accept. Surely we are each born with a unique certain something, a unique personality? The personality is the more readily recognisable of the two, but the absence of an explanation for it is a stumbling block to taking identity acquisition in full stride. So I have made the personality the target of this essay because if, like Frankenstein, I can 'construct' a personality...

I will not offer a definition right away because it is so tricky to define and what I am getting at will become clear as the essay goes on; so just some preliminary thoughts. We can recognise, even if only in vague terms, that someone we have known from childhood has a personality, in the same way that we recognise the person physically. Their personality appeared early and stayed constant. If someone's personality changes dramatically we look for the traumatic experience that might explain it, or signs of psychopathology. How do we get a personality? Surely it must be a mix of what we inherited and what our environment does to us?

There is no model for the mechanism that generates an individual's personality, which is perhaps not a surprise for something so difficult to define, but any theory of mind and human identity that is worth the candle must be able to explain it. This essay explains features of the identity that not only correspond to our ideas about the personality but are fundamental to our humanity.

The personality is formed during the early stage of identity construction and the mechanism of language acquisition is of fundamental importance in the process. Given that it is a unique physical individual that has a personality, the personality is nevertheless acquired, not inherited. This is the model that I want to explain, and of course it means rejecting ideas about the role of inheritance. For example...

In Agatha Christie's 'Elephants can Remember' (1972), one of the protagonists announces: *'You must admit that in a marriage it is necessary to think about children. I mean the children to come. We are aware nowadays that heredity is more important than the environment in which a child is raised. Heredity imprints certain character traits and so can in itself pose serious risks...'* 'It is true' said Poirot. Later in the story: *'In reality, Dorothea was destined for a tragic end, not by any fault of her own or by circumstances, but by her very birth, by her hereditary factors.'*

In the film 'Lord of the Rings', Arwen asks: *Why do you fear the past? You are*

Isildur's heir, not Isildur himself. You are not bound to his fate... Aragorn replies: The same blood flows in my veins, the same weakness... (He makes out OK though, as you probably know.)

In the film *Dune* (2021), Lady Jessica explains: *'For thousands of years we have been carefully crossing bloodlines to bring forth...'* Paul: *'The One?'* Lady Jessica: *'...a mind... powerful enough to bridge space and time.'*

These ideas are innocent enough in their context (maybe, but they lead in a dangerous direction) and they are also a part of everyday thinking. For example, an exasperated family member is struggling with your personality: *"Oh, you're just like your mother!"* and you think: *'She was just like her father; so it must run in the family - and there's not much I can do about it'.*

With these examples I am highlighting the 'heredity' account of the human identity and personality; it seems to be such a natural explanation. Powerful emotional forces are operating and the belief in the inheritance of the identity provides caring people with an apparently rational basis for their emotional link with their ancestors and living members of their family. They would probably explain to me that it's not just a question of what one thinks about these admired ancestors and living loved ones, as if one was free to make up one's own mind.

Nevertheless, I'll state it bluntly: our personal identities, emotions and values are in no way dictated by our genes, they are *acquired*. It follows that we have no inherited link to the identities of our ancestors, and, closer to home, it also follows that the identities of children are not linked by inheritance to the identities of their parents. (!... I appreciate the difficulty.) There are plenty of links – you may well be just like your mother - but they are not inherited. Genes that compel you to be like your mother don't exist. In fact the *acquisition of identity* emphasises our personal responsibility for our ties, a responsibility that is masked by thinking in terms of genetic heritage.

My first task is to explain as clearly as I can the early stages of the construction of an acquired identity (and, with a much better model, justify the rejection of genetic determinism). In principle it's very simple: genes construct our bodies but social interaction and language construct our minds and identities. Your genes made you *male*, your testicles made you an adult *male*, but society, which of course includes your family, made you a *man* with a gender identity somewhere along the gender 'spectrum' that we are nowadays much more comfortable with.

My explanation of the construction of the personality and identity begins with the metaphor of a sheet of paper in the brain of a baby. It's an old idea that has some important limitations but it sidesteps the problem of what is not yet known about the complexities of the baby's developing brain. Mental activity can be thought of as the expression of what is on the sheet. The crucial issue, the Dorothea dilemma, is whether

the sheet of the newborn already has elements written on it that have been created from the baby's genes, or whether a sheet is blank at birth and is written on afterwards to create an entirely acquired identity. Whichever, the personality also has to be accounted for. (The sheet *itself* has to be thought of as created by the genes, and so, just as our bodies may be more or less athletic (say), baby sheets may be bigger or smaller (say) - but I am treating that as a different issue from the question of the identity and the mind. How we treat each other because our bodies are different or because our 'sheets' are different in size is a moral issue. And morality is a social construction.)

I want to illustrate both the possibilities that I mentioned. I'll look at the Dorothea model first: aspects of the mental identity are inherited, so there are messages from the past on the sheet to create a natural innate identity and personality...

The genetic kaleidoscope creates – not forgetting the mother of course - a body, a brain and a mental core...

The purple rectangle is the sheet of paper, coded by the genes (or Smarties if you prefer) and the squiggle on the sheet represents an innate set of instructions or 'core', also coded by the genes. Since the core is hereditary, it's code will be present in the germ cells. To keep the illustration simple I have not included the additional acquired information that would appear on the identity-sheet later in life; not even the most ardent Naturist believes that there is no Nurture. I haven't been able to come up with any reasonable suggestions as to how a genetically coded core may exert its effect on later acquired language to impose a personality, so I am happy to move on: the following adaptation of the illustration shows the correct alternative.

The genetic kaleidoscope creates a totally blank 'sheet'...

The blank sheet metaphor is useful because it suggests the idea of being written on, and allows me to use a pencil in the illustration to indicate that what is acquired is language. This 'correct' description is all about language acquisition and there are no genes involved. So no need for sperm or eggs in the illustration either because no elements of the acquired identity can be transmitted genetically (to your children). Again to keep the illustration simple, later language-information additions that will be written onto the sheet are left out – but they are of central importance in this model. It is the life-history of language acquisition and storage, accessed by the brain's language handling mechanism, the ensemble, that explains the identity, and certain characteristics of that ensemble create a personality.

What I haven't indicated on the later sheets in the illustration is the language information that was retained because important at that moment, then re-used repeatedly and reinforced in importance in the structure of the language store; otherwise this information is forgotten. So what is retained on the sheet represents acquired values. The mental identity is constructed from the values and attitudes acquired in the kindergarten and the university of life and they are used often enough as the starting points for 'new' thoughts that they result in patterns of thought and behaviour that may well stay with an individual throughout life. Observers label these attitudes and behaviour as the 'personality' of the individual. The individual physically acting out these attitudes feels in possession of an identity.

The letter represents current thinking and is influenced by the 'personality' of the value-history. Attitudes are not necessarily oppressive of course.

I think the 'ensemble' model does the job, almost; but there's still the nagging feeling that there is more to us than a tissue composed of language. I may be able to do better if I can answer the following question: is there something special about the earliest acquired language information that makes it in some way more fundamental to the identity than the language handled later? Does the process of early acquisition embed elements of the identity more permanently and more 'deeply' than later language-handling activity? It's a possibility with a possible explanation: the links that the brain forges between language and the body. So to explain how such a core might be possible, I will have to introduce the model for language acquisition in the early days and years.

In a previous essay (The Acquisition of Language) I gave an account of the relationship between the baby brain and language, summarised in this illustration.

The human brain is a mammalian brain and only has at its disposal what such brains

can ancestrally do. The entirely new challenge of handling language was met, and is met in the development of a baby's brain, by treating language as a form of movement. For a brain, 'movement' is the musculoskeletal system of the moving body. So another way of representing a language core in the baby's brain would be...

Not so much a sheet...

In this model, the core language and the body are inextricably linked and the 'body', as presented in the brain, is an integral and permanent part of the identity. It is a live identity, where the body plays a role in the personality and maybe our get-up-and-go as well. However that doesn't change the fact that it is by the language-body link that the driver, language, gets into the driving seat. This link is the mechanism of the dominance of language, a dominance that must depend above all on the relationship between our constructed identities and our emotions: very early on, human communication constructs a human, social version of the emotions, entirely replacing the hard-wired reflex version of 'solo' animals. A 'theory of emotions' is called for, but given the fundamental importance of this core development, you can see how easily things might go wrong for us!

Commendably brief and to the point, obviously this essay is only the skimpiest of sketches of what most likely takes place in the construction of the personality and identity, but the model has several merits: it's on the right lines, it eases the concern that an acquired identity lacks a nitty-gritty, and it removes the confusion about the role of genetics and focuses the attention on baby Dorothea's environment. Which is, above all, us; and let's face it, if we had a better idea of what we are contributing and how communication works, the world might be a much better place than it is - emphasising the importance and possible fruitfulness of understanding our identity in the way the essay describes.

PS: The Agatha extract is a back-translation from my French copy, so cut me some slack for the exact wording.